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Международный научный журнал

ВЫПУСК
10, 2024

*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

Научно-исследовательский институт «Физики резонансных ядерных реакций» является научным учреждением, осуществляющим фундаментальные, прикладные научные исследования и инновационные разработки в области науки, техники, культуры и просвещения.

Все науки. №10, 2024

Международный научный
журнал

Издательские решения
По лицензии Ridero
2024

THE ROLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING LEGAL CULTURE

UDK: 304.2/340.115.7

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Abstract. This article discusses the place and role of the education system in the formation of legal awareness among the population in our country, the means of providing legal education to young people, and a number of fundamental reforms being implemented to further develop the legal awareness and legal culture of the population.

Keywords: law, legal consciousness, legal culture, legal education, law, concept.

Special attention has been paid to the formation of an attitude of respect for human rights and freedoms, to raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, and to increasing the level of legal literacy of citizens in society. In particular, in the field of improving legal culture, first of all, work on legal education and upbringing is not being carried out systematically and coherently. For many years, this issue has been viewed as the work of law enforcement agencies and certain state bodies, and the participation of the family, neighborhood and other institutions of civil society has not been sufficiently ensured. [1]

There was no comprehensive approach to the formation of legal immunity against factors that negatively affect the legal education of young people, to instill in each person a sense of respect for laws and morals, loyalty to national values, and intolerance towards violations.

The general definition of tasks for improving the legal knowledge of the population and the absence of a clear effective mechanism for their implementation indicate that work to improve legal culture in society is being carried out ineffectively.

The insufficient implementation of efforts to instill in the population the ideas of maintaining a balance between personal interests and the interests of society in raising legal awareness and legal culture also has a serious negative impact on ensuring the rule of law.

The population's insufficient legal knowledge, as well as the fact that they rarely use the opportunity to appeal against unlawful decisions of state bodies, leads to instances of officials violating the rights and legitimate interests of citizens.

At the same time, a number of problems and shortcomings remain that hinder the formation of an attitude of respect for human rights and freedoms, the improvement of the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, and the increase in the level of legal literacy of citizens in society. In particular:

Firstly, the work on raising legal awareness and legal culture in society is not being systematically and coherently organized. There is no effective mechanism for conveying legal information in society, in the family, in the neighborhood, in educational institutions and organizations. The ideas of ensuring a balance between personal interests and the interests of society are not sufficiently instilled in the minds of the population, especially civil servants;

secondly, educational processes in the continuing education system are not being carried out in harmony with legal education, and the history, religion, traditions, and national values of the Uzbek people are not being relied on in forming the legal culture of the population, especially the youth;

thirdly, in organizing events to improve legal culture, an effective system of cooperation with non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions has not been created, and work has not been organized on the basis of the principle of social partnership;

fourth, no specific targeted measures have been identified to form legal immunity against factors that negatively affect the legal education of young people;

fifth, the active participation of state bodies and other sectoral services in the organization and implementation of targeted legal awareness-raising activities in society is not ensured, and high effectiveness and efficiency in this regard are not observed;

sixth, legal activities are still carried out in traditional ways, through simple meetings, innovative methods of promotion, including web technologies, are not used in this regard, and there are not enough legal websites;

Seventh, there are no legal mechanisms to encourage projects aimed at increasing legal literacy, events in this regard are organized only for the sake of publicity, and the publication and distribution of legal literature and scientific research to improve legal knowledge are being carried out ineffectively.

Uzbekistan is boldly moving forward on the path of building a democratic, rule-of-law state and forming a just civil society, taking a strong place in the

world community. Thanks to stability and order, interethnic harmony and civil harmony, our young state is gaining trust and respect.

Our country is undergoing large-scale reforms in the fields of economy, politics, state building, legal system and spiritual transformation of society. The legal basis for the reforms being carried out has been created. The legal framework of socio-political life is being consistently strengthened and improved.

The study of the philosophical, social, economic, psychological and legal problems of the essence, content, structural structure and manifestation of legal culture, as well as the identification of methods for its formation and further improvement, should be considered a priority area of scientific research.

It is especially relevant to conduct scientific research on such pressing problems as the relationship between the general and legal culture of the individual; legal culture and legal character; the role of law in the formation of social consciousness; legal education and social activity of the population; forms and methods of influencing legal consciousness; psychological aspects of legal consciousness; social distortions and negative changes in legal consciousness; legal culture of various strata and social groups of the population.

In order to develop the sociological basis for studying the problems of legal culture, to determine the real picture of the state of legal culture in society as a whole and the legal culture of various segments of the population, it is necessary to conduct surveys and use other methods of determining public opinion about law, its social value and regulatory function. Particular attention should be paid to studying the pedagogical problems of forming legal culture. The Ministries of Public Education, Higher and Secondary Specialized Education should develop a scientifically based methodology for legal education of young people with the participation of interested organizations. Taking into account the specific characteristics of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is important to publish and expand the use of the results of scientific research on improving legal culture in foreign countries, and to establish an exchange of scientific information in this area.

The holding of scientific and practical conferences, seminars, the increase in the publication of scientific, popular scientific literature and reference books should make a significant contribution to the strengthening of scientific research on issues of improving the legal culture of the population, the popularization of scientific knowledge. The development of our homeland and the success of reforms largely depend on the level of legal awareness and legal culture of the people. The political activity of a person, his truly civic attitude, and his aspiration for democratic reforms are important factors in the speedy achievement of the set goals.

High legal culture is the foundation of a democratic society and a manifestation of the maturity of the legal system. It is a factor that actively

influences various life processes in society, promotes the cohesion of citizens and all social groups, ensures and strengthens the integrity and order of society. Respect for the law is one of the main requirements for a legal society and the effective functioning of political and legal systems.

Legal culture — general of culture inseparable structural part. Humans in mind so confidence decision to find necessary, legal to knowledge has was and them in practice applicable just one person civilized and to be considered educated possible. Society and state development current status legal relationship all of the participants legal culture, legal literacy every one-sided increase demand Legal culture legal knowledge, legal belief and consistent practical activity set as society and state in front of standing of tasks successful solution to be completed provides.

In our country human rights and interests provision, social life democratization for conditions create and legal state the basics formation out of necessity come came out without this National program acceptance Legal culture formation and promotion in the field state policy following to the principles based on: human rights and of freedoms precedence; Constitution and of the law superiority; democracy social justice; scientificity; continuity; legal in education succession and generality; legal of information everyone for openness; legal upbringing and legal of education unit and to them differentiated approach. High legal culture formation according to state of the policy priority directions of the following consists of :

- citizen, society and of the state mutual in their relationship population legal culture and social activity the rise to provide;
- population legal culture in formation citizens himself himself/herself management bodies, public associations, public information of tools role strengthen;
- the population legal information with provision, popular science legal literature publication to be done and distribution state by support;
- legal education and legal upbringing tools and methods improvement;
- legal education, personnel preparation and again preparation modern system development;
- legal of culture scientific the basics research to reach encouragement, socio-legal research organization to grow;
- national traditions and world from experience use based on population legal consciousness and legal culture to form.

Population legal culture formation according to state policy successful done increase, one from the side of society every one member legal of knowledge certain level by mastering to receive for necessary was conditions creation, second from the side — different social of groups to oneself typical features into account received without legal education to differentiate in mind holds.

Uzbekistan Republic President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's January 9, 2019, address to the nation legal mind and legal culture promotion system fundamentally improvement Decree No. PF-5618 «On wide public legal consciousness, legal culture, legal literacy level on the rise practical importance profession This will In the decree population legal consciousness and legal culture to elevate, in society citizens legal literacy level to increase obstacle doer following problem and disadvantages preserved remaining counting passed. Including legal culture in the promotion, the most first of all, legal education and upbringing regarding affairs systematic and integral take not going. Legal mind and legal culture in promotion personal interests and society interests between balance storage ideas population to the mind to absorb of work enough take It is also illegal not to go. priority to provide his/her own serious negative impact showing.

Come on, count. passed this problem and shortcomings a little analysis as Let's go out. The most at the end brought our past is» personal» interests and society interests between balance storage ideas population to the mind from «absorption» Let's start. Our country leader their own many lecture and in their speeches state and society progressive to hold of the general public to work rotation need, this for every one citizen his/her own this regarding firmly citizenship position manifestation to be able to, to be a citizen personal interest no when society in the interest of column that it should not be emphasizing Of course, this in vain it's not. The reason is, where? personal benefit society and state in the interest of column sheep that, that on the ground serious problem appearance will be. Saying necessary if corruption, greed and other vices to the body It comes. These two benefit between balance storage extremely important. From this come out, first of all wide public between this balance every how to keep even in conditions the idea systematic propaganda to do necessary.

«Legal» education and upbringing regarding affairs systematic and integral take It is also true that «it is not going». Preschool education from institutions starting from the top study to their homeland was in stages mutual integral dependency is not enough. Or preschool education in institutions teachable legal lessons for textbook and study manuals, visual weapons is it enough said Answer «yes» to the question. to give difficult. In this regard here this aged children to the mind legal culture how methods with absorption necessary said serious matter in mind is thrown away. In this place psychologists and lawyers with in cooperation legal lessons study of literature working exit to the goal according to. [2]

As of March 1, 2019 until in youth legal mind and legal culture promotion, especially their in mind corruption society and country prosperity for extreme negative defect eating promote to do aimed at study materials preparation appearance to do; young generation legal consciousness and legal culture promotion according to education institutions the right protection doer organs

with cooperation to do effective mechanisms expansion measures see such as serious tasks uploaded.

22 years ago before High Assembly decision with acceptance» In society» legal culture promotion National Program «from» that much time from the past then him/her from today 's demand and from the soul come out update necessity was born. Attention do it today on the day how many socio-political, economic changes event is giving. This from a point of view this Decree with In society legal culture promotion concept confirmed, then one row important importance has directions marked.

Indeed, the individual, the state and society mutual in their relationship the law, in it legal standards solution doer importance profession It will. every one person's society and state in front of social responsibility defines. In society legal culture promotion concept to oneself typical the most important in terms of one, legal upbringing formation and legal culture promotion initially from the family beginning necessity is fixed.

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Все науки. №10, 2024
Международный научный журнал

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ISBN 978-5-0065-1875-9

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